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INVESTIGATION ON SYNERGISTIC ANTIBACTERIAL PROPERTIES OF SILVER NANOPARTICLES ENCAPSULATED WITH DIFFERENT STABILIZING AGENTS

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ABSTRACT

The emergence and spread of antibiotic resistance is an alarming concern in clinical practice. This would lead to the development of new antibacterial agents from natural and inorganic substances. In the present scenario, nanomaterials are the leading requirements in the field of bionanotechnology and nanomedicine owing to their high surface to volume ratio. Hence the present study has been focused to evaluate the antibacterial activity of stabilized and non-stabilized silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) against selected bacterial pathogens. Silver nanoparticles were fabricated by chemical reduction method. The size of the particles was determined by X-ray diffraction pattern (XRD) and it ranges from 18-43 nm. The morphology of the particles was observed through scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Bactericidal effect of AgNPs was done by agar well diffusion method. Bacterial sensitivity was found to vary depending on the microbial species. The stabilized AgNPs showed excellent antibacterial activity (22 mm) to *Streptococcus epidermis* than the other experimental strains used. Two way ANOVA test revealed that the function of AgNPs on bacterial pathogens is statistically significant. Therefore, our results suggest that chemically mediated silver nanoparticles could act as an effective alternative for the development of new antimicrobial agent to combat resistance problem.

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INTRODUCTION

The emergence and the development of more and more strains turn resistance to antibiotics and bactericides is an alarming concern in clinical practice. The pharmaceutical companies and the researchers are searching for designing novel antibacterial formulations. Development of new, cost effective antimicrobial agents has been an objective of research activity. The most effective vicinity of nanotechnology is the competence of modulating metals into their nanosize¹, which offers unique approaches to probe and control a wide variety of biological and medical processes that occur at nanometer length and is believed to have a successful collision on biology and medicine^{2,3}. Nanoparticles seems potential option when compared to the conventional materials used⁴ and play a crucial role in inhibiting bacterial growth because of their high reactivity and the large surface to volume ratio⁵. Among a range of metal nanoparticles, AgNPs reveal strong inhibitory and bactericidal effects⁶. Antibacterial activity of silver containing materials used in the medicine to diminish infections in burn treatments and arthroplasty, as well as to prevent bacterial colonization on prostheses, catheters, vascular grafts, dental materials, stainless steel materials and human skin. Silver nanoparticles also exhibit a potent cytoprotective activity towards HIV-infected cells⁷. Silver containing materials can be employed to abolish microorganisms on textile fabrics or they can be used for water treatment⁵. Due to the extensive progress and application of nanoparticles in miscellaneous field, a problem arises as to the relation between the environmental safety and useful properties of nanosystem. Production of Ag-NPs can be achieved through different methods. The drawback of chemical synthesis without stabilizing agent is agglomeration of nanoparticles. Agglomeration takes place primarily through direct interparticle interaction such as Vander Waals forces and magnetic interactions. It reduces the specific surface area and the interfacial free energy, thereby diminishing particle reactivity. To prevent the aggregation, the surface of the particles was passivated through the layer of stabilizer. A stabilizer can enhance dispersion and steric hindrance⁸. In this study green chemicals such as starch, CMC, and chitosan were used as stabilizers. All these three polysaccharide derivatives are well-known food grade ingredient, nontoxic, biodegradable, and biocompatible biopolymers which were widely employed as tissue-engineering scaffolds and in drug delivery applications⁹. However, to the best of our knowledge, the bactericidal effect of selected bacterial pathogens using silver nanoparticles with different stabilizing agents not yet been studied. The synthesis method reported in this work might be helpful for providing an economic route for the large scale production of highly stable and biologically compatible silver nanoparticles.

The goal of this work was fabrication and characterization of silver nanoparticles with and without toxic-free, biocompatible, natural stabilizing agents and the bactericidal activity was comparatively evaluated.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Silver nitrate (AgNO_3), Trisodium citrate ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_7\text{Na}_3$), Sodium hydroxide (NaOH), Sodium borohydride (NaBH_4), Ascorbic acid ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_6$), Acetic acid (CH_3COOH), D-Glucose, Starch, CarboxyMethyl Cellulose (CMC), Chitosan were purchased from Himedia (P) Ltd, Mumbai, were used as starting materials without further purification. Milli-Q water was used for the fabrication of nanoparticles throughout the experiment.

Methods

Preparation of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs)

The silver nanoparticles were prepared using chemical reduction method¹⁰. In this method, 150 ml of 1×10^{-3} M AgNO_3 solution was heated to boiling. To this solution, 15 ml of 1% trisodium citrate was added drop by

drop under constant stirring. Reaction mixture was heated until the solution color changed to pale yellow. Then, it was removed from heating element and stirred until cooled to room temperature.

Mechanism of reaction could be expressed as follows:

Preparation of starch stabilized silver nanoparticles (AgNPs/S)

According to description of Vasileva *et al.*¹¹, the starch aqueous solution (0.2% (w/v), 32 ml) was stirred for 15 min. Then 16 ml of 0.001 M AgNO₃ aqueous solution was added under constant stirring. The mixture was stirred for 10 min to allow the diffusion of metal ions to the capping agent. The reducing agent solution (0.1 M, 480 µl) was injected followed by the addition of 2.4 ml 0.1 M NaOH aqueous solution. The temperature of 30 ± 2°C was kept constant in the magnetic stirrer and the reaction could be completed within 60 min after the first color appearance.

Preparation of CMC stabilized silver nanoparticles (AgNPs/CMC)

The CMC stabilized AgNPs synthesis procedure was same according to the description of Vasileva *et al.*¹¹ instead of starch; CMC was used as a stabilizer.

Preparation of chitosan stabilized silver nanoparticles (AgNPs/CH)

Chitosan stabilized silver nanoparticles were prepared via seed-mediated growth¹². In the first step, a stock solution of silver particles called seeds was prepared in Milli-Q water by reduction reaction of silver nitrate with sodium borohydride. In a typical procedure, one volume of aqueous solution of silver nitrate (10 ml, 2.9×10⁻⁴ M) was mixed with an aqueous solution of trisodium citrate (10 ml, 2.5×10⁻⁴ M) and cooled in an ice-bath under vigorous stirring. To this mixture, an aqueous solution of sodium borohydride (0.6 ml, 0.1 M) was added dropwise which results in the formation of a bright yellow solution. The as-prepared seed solution was stored in the dark for 2-3 h before use in order for any excess borohydride reacts with water. In the second step, a mixture of aqueous solution of trisodium citrate (35 mm, 200 µl), ascorbic acid (0.1 M, 50 µl), chitosan in 1% acetic acid (2 mg ml⁻¹, 10 ml), seeds (200 µl), and AgNO₃ solution (0.01 M, 300 µl) was added dropwise under continuous magnetic stirring. The growth of the silver nanoparticles was finished after 5 min at 35 ± 2°C. All the above mentioned synthesized silver colloids were centrifuged at 10000 rpm for 30 min. The resultant solution was washed three times in Milli-Q water and once in ethanol solution. The supernatant solution was discarded and particles were dried overnight in hot air oven at 60°C. The dried particles were taken for further analysis.

CHARACTERIZATION OF SILVER NANOPARTICLES

Visual inspection

The reduction of metal ions was roughly monitored by visual inspection of the reaction solution by color change.

X-ray diffraction pattern

The crystallographic analysis of the samples was performed by powder X-ray diffraction. The X-ray diffraction patterns were recorded in the scanning mode on an X'pert PROPAN analytical instrument operated at 40 kV and a current of 30 mA with Cu α radiation (λ=1.54060 Å). The diffraction intensities were recorded from 10.02° to 79.92° in 2θ angles. The diffraction intensities were compared with the standard JCPDS files. The software gave the information about the crystal structure of the particle and the average size of the particles can be estimated using the Debye-Scherrer equation¹³,

$$D = k\lambda / \beta \cos\theta$$

Where D is the thickness of the nanocrystal, 'k' constant, 'λ' wavelength of X-rays, 'β' width at half-height of the reflection after correction for the instrumental broadening at Bragg's angle 2θ, 'θ' Bragg's angle.

Scanning electron microscopy

Morphology of the synthesized silver nanoparticles was observed with the scanning electron microscope (JSM 35 CF JEOL) operated at a resolution of 60 Å at 15 kv. The solid samples were sprinkled on the adhesive carbon tape which is supported on a metallic disk. The sample surface images were taken at different magnifications. The magnification of the microscope was 5.0 Kv. The scale was about 8.4 mm to 5 µm.

ANTIBACTERIAL STUDY OF SILVER NANOPARTICLES

Bacterial cultures

In the present experiment, the following bacterial pathogens namely *Bacillus cereus*, *Edwardsilla tarda*, *Escherichia coli*, *Flexibacter sp.*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus epidermis* and *Vibrio vulnificus* were grown on nutrient agar plate and maintained in the nutrient agar slants at 4°C. Overnight culture in the nutrient broth was used in the present experiment.

Bactericidal effect of silver nanoparticles

The antibacterial activity of synthesized silver nanoparticles with and without stabilizers was evaluated using agar-well diffusion method. Pure cultures of each strain were subcultured in nutrient broth for 12 h at 37°C. A 20 ml volume of Mueller Hinton agar medium was poured into each petriplate on horizontally leveled surface. Each bacterial strain was swabbed uniformly into the individual plates using sterile cotton swabs. Wells of 6 mm diameter were made onto each bacterium inoculated agar plates using sterile gel puncture. 100 µl of silver nanoparticle suspension was introduced into the corresponding wells. The bactericidal activity was determined by a clear inhibition zone around the sample loaded well after incubation of plates overnight at 37°C.

Assessment of increase in fold area

According to Fayaz *et al.*¹⁴, increase in fold area was assessed by calculating the mean surface area of the inhibition zone generated by unstabilized and stabilized silver nanoparticles. The fold increase area was calculated by the equation,

$$\text{Fold increase (\%)} = (b-a)/a \times 100$$

Where a and b refer to the zones of inhibition for unstabilized and stabilized silver nanoparticles.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

CHARACTERIZATION OF SILVER NANOPARTICLES

Visual inspection

The appearance of pale yellow color colloidal solution for silver nanoparticles, brown for starch and CMC and greenish for chitosan stabilized silver colloids in the reaction mixture indicate the formation of AgNPs (Fig 1).

AgNPs AgNPs/S AgNPs/CMC AgNPs/CH

Fig.1: Freshly prepared colloidal solutions of silver nanoparticles

The formation of color in the reaction solution was due to the excitation of surface plasmon vibration in the silver nanoparticles.

X-ray diffractogram

Fig 2 shows the crystalline nature of the as prepared AgNPs. The intensive diffraction peaks at

Fig. 2: X-ray diffraction patterns of synthesized silver nanoparticles

2θ value of 38.11° , 38.33° , 38.06° , and 38.04° indexed as (111) lattice plane of face centered cubic (fcc) form for AgNPs and stabilized AgNPs respectively unequivocally indicated that the particles are made of pure silver. In the obtained spectrum, the Bragg's peak position and their intensities were compared with the standard JCPDS files. The size of the AgNPs was found to be 43.92 nm (silver), 29.28 nm (starch), 14.06 nm (CMC), and 21.95 nm (chitosan). This finding is very much closer to the earliest reports^{1,11,15}.

Scanning electron microscopy

The scanning electron microscopy of synthesized silver nanoparticles reveals that the particles are spherical and hexagonal in nature (Fig 3).

Fig. 3: Scanning electron micrograph of silver nanoparticles

The micrograph shows that the AgNPs do not appear as discrete particles but form much larger dendritic flocs whose size could reach micron scale. The aggregation is attributed due to the interparticular interactions among the AgNPs.

BACTERICIDAL EFFECT OF SILVER NANOPARTICLES

The antibacterial activity of silver nanoparticles has been reported against bacterial pathogens namely *Bacillus cereus*, *Edwardsiella tarda*, *Escherichia coli*, *Flexibacter sp.*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus epidermis*, and *Vibrio vulnificus* (Fig 4). Silver nanoparticles exhibited good antibacterial activity against experimental pathogens used. The diameter of inhibition zone (mm) among silver nanoparticles against test strains is given in Table 1.

Fig. 4: Antibacterial activity of unstabilized and stabilized silver nanoparticles

Table 1: Antibacterial activity of silver nanoparticles with and without stabilizers against selected bacterial pathogens

Pathogens	Zone of Inhibition (mm)			
	AgNPs	AgNPs/S	AgNPs/CMC	AgNPs/CH
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	9	11	14	11
<i>Edwardsiella tarda</i>	8	8	15	11
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	6	7	13	13
<i>Flexibacter sp.</i>	10	11	18	11
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	7	7	17	12
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	7	6	14	14
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	15	11	16	11
<i>Streptococcus epidermis</i>	11	14	22	13
<i>Vibrio vulnificus</i>	11	16	17	12

In our experimental study, stabilized AgNPs exhibited higher sensitivity against bacterial pathogens. The enhanced surface to volume ratio of the stabilized AgNPs is responsible for increased zone of inhibition. From

these results it was supported that the bactericidal effect was size and dose dependent. The bactericidal effect was higher in the case being smaller particle size⁷. The stabilized AgNPs with large surface area could be tightly absorbed into the surface of the bacterial cells so as to disrupt the membrane. From our results, CMC stabilized AgNPs produced excellent bactericidal activity followed by chitosan, and starch stabilized AgNPs. The highest antibacterial sensitivity was observed for CMC stabilized AgNPs against *Streptococcus epidermis* (22 mm), Chitosan stabilized AgNPs against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (14 mm), Starch stabilized AgNPs against *Streptococcus epidermis* (14 mm), Unstabilized Silver nanoparticles produced maximum sensitivity against *Staphylococcus aureus* (15 mm). The exact mechanism of action of AgNPs on the microbes is still unknown but the possible mechanism may be the nanoparticles get attachment to the cell membrane and penetrate into the cell. The AgNPs make pits on the outer membrane of the bacteria by attachment of sulfur containing membrane proteins¹⁶ which would lead to the leakage of intracellular components, thus killing the bacterial cells. Inside the cell the AgNPs interact with phosphorus containing compounds like DNA. Due to this, DNA gets condensed and loses its replication ability and cellular protein mechanism also inactivated. It also attacks respiratory chain and cell division of microbes. In another way the nanoparticles enhances the bactericidal activity by releasing the silver ions into the bacterial cells¹⁷. In *E.coli*, Ag⁺ inhibits the uptake of phosphate and release of phosphate, mannitol, proline, and glutamate from the cell¹⁸. The positive charge on Ag⁺ is an important factor for its antibacterial nature, through electrostatic interaction it binds with the negatively charged cell membrane of the organism and inhibits the respiration process finally leads to death^{19,20}. Two-way ANOVA test revealed that the functions of AgNPs on bacterial pathogens are statistically significant. (F = 6.67 and 7.55; P<0.05; Table 2).

The stabilized silver nanoparticles produced superior inhibitory effect than non-stabilized silver. The percentage of fold increase was calculated and given in Tables 3-5. The highest percentage of fold increase was found for CMC stabilized AgNPs against *Escherichia coli* followed by *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

Table 2: Two-way analysis of variance for the data on inhibition zone (mm) of silver nanoparticles against bacterial pathogens

Source of variation	SS	DF	MS	'F' Value	P
Total variance	480.75	35	-	-	
Variance between AgNPs	256.30	8	32.04	6.67	<0.05
Variance between bacterial pathogens	109	3	36.33	7.55	<0.05
Error variance	115.45	24	4.81	-	

SS - Sum of Squares; DF – Degrees of Freedom; MS – Mean Square.

Note: P < 0.05 is statistically significant

Table 3: Percentage of fold increase of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) and starch stabilized silver nanoparticles (AgNPs/S) against selected bacterial pathogens

Bacterial Pathogens	Zone of Inhibition (mm)		Increased Zone Size (mm)	Percentage of Fold Increase F= ((b-a)/a)*100
	AgNPs (a)	AgNPs/S (b)		
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	9	11	2	22.22
<i>Edwardsiella tarda</i>	8	8	0	0
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	6	7	1	16.67
<i>Flexibacter sp.</i>	10	11	1	10
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	7	7	0	0
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	7	6	-	-
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	15	11	-	-
<i>Streptococcus epidermis</i>	11	14	3	27.27
<i>Vibrio vulnificus</i>	11	16	5	45.45

Table 4: Percentage of fold increase of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) and CMC stabilized silver nanoparticles (AgNPs/CMC) against selected bacterial pathogens

Bacterial Pathogens	Zone of Inhibition (mm)		Increased Zone Size (mm)	Percentage of Fold Increase F= ((b-a)/a)*100
	AgNPs (a)	AgNPs/CMC (b)		
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	9	14	5	55.56
<i>Edwardsiella tarda</i>	8	15	7	87.50
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	6	13	7	116.67
<i>Flexibacter sp.</i>	10	18	8	80.00
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	7	17	10	142.86
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	7	14	7	100
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	15	16	1	06.67
<i>Streptococcus epidermis</i>	11	22	11	100
<i>Vibrio vulnificus</i>	11	17	6	54.55

Table 5: Percentage of fold increase of silver nanoparticles (AgNPs) and chitosan stabilized silver nanoparticles (AgNPs/CH) against selected bacterial pathogens

Bacterial Pathogens	Zone of Inhibition (mm)		Increased Zone Size (mm)	Percentage of Fold Increase F= ((b-a)/a)*100
	AgNPs (a)	AgNPs/CH (b)		
<i>Bacillus cereus</i>	9	11	2	22.22
<i>Edwardsiella tarda</i>	8	11	3	37.50
<i>Escherichia coli</i>	6	13	7	116.67
<i>Flexibacter sp.</i>	10	11	1	10
<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	7	12	5	71.43
<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	7	14	7	100
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	15	11	-	-
<i>Streptococcus epidermis</i>	11	13	2	18.18
<i>Vibrio vulnificus</i>	11	12	1	9.09

CONCLUSION

From this study, AgNPs with and without stabilizing agent are synthesized by chemical reduction method. The synthesized particle size is calculated by XRD, and its morphology was observed through SEM. The stabilized silver nanoparticles exhibit better bactericidal activity than unstabilized one due to increased surface area. Results from this study support the hypothesis that the toxic-free, biocompatible, natural stabilized silver nanoparticles prepared in a simple and cost effective manner which are suitable for the formulation of new types of bactericidal materials.

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